

ANIMATED FILMS AS A REFLECTION OF THE NATIONAL AND LINGUISTIC PICTURE OF THE WORLD

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Abstract: The concept of a national picture of the world is inseparable from the concept of a linguistic picture of the world. The formation of these concepts is so interconnected, their interaction, interdependence and mutual influence are so close that for many years there have been debates about which of them is primary – language or consciousness itself. In this article we tried to show that modern animated films can be used as a means of reflection of the linguistic and national picture of the world.

Key words: Animation, linguistic picture of the world, national picture of the world, linguoculturology, national-cultural identification

There are more than 2.000 nationalities recorded in the modern world. The term nationality refers to a person's belonging to a certain ethnic community of people, differing in the peculiarities of language, culture, psychology, traditions, customs, lifestyle. Due to two competing trends in the development of modern society – globalization and glocalization – the problem arises, on the one hand, the preservation of national identity, the preservation and popularization of the national linguistic picture of the world, on the other – adaptation to the surrounding reality by acculturation, adaptation, localization, if necessary, further co-existence.

Today, the linguistic picture of the world is one of the basic concepts in many areas of humanitarian knowledge. It expresses "the specifics of man and his being, his relationship with the world, the most important conditions of his existence in the world (Postovalova, 1988) and is studied in philosophy, psychology, sociology, anthropology. Recently, the linguistic picture of the world has been increasingly strengthening its positions in the terminological apparatus of philological and related disciplines: sociolinguistics, linguoculturology, psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, teaching foreign languages and cultures.

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close that for many years there have been disputes about which of them is primary – language or consciousness itself. The peculiarities of national perception reflected in the language, through the semantics of the stable images, expressions (collocations) of words included in the structure, encode certain cultural information. The formation and preservation of the national linguistic picture of the world has a spiral character: from the moment of birth, a person hears lullabies, fairy tales, etc., thereby joining the national culture, and then, consciously or unconsciously, develops this accumulated knowledge, which acquire different forms of realization.

The linguistic picture of the world, which has become the object of study of both linguoculturology and linguistics proper, is, in the words of I.A. Sternin, "the totality of people's ideas about reality fixed in units of language at a certain stage of its development, the idea of reality reflected in language signs and their meanings – the linguistic ordering of objects and phenomena embedded in the system the meanings of the words information about the world".

The picture of the world and the linguistic picture of the world, in particular, are formed under the influence of a significant number of factors, both external and internal, which are in a relationship of interaction and mutual interdependence. The coding system of national-cultural marking, motivation and specificity differs in its methods and forms of expression, content in various languagesystem (V.Kornilov, 2003). "The linguistic picture of the world includes a value dimension of linguistically relevant understanding of reality. Within the framework of this measurements are contrasted with values, norms and customs as hierarchically organized formats for storing knowledge of behavioral attitudes in typical communication situations".

The linguistic picture of the world is largely based on the concept of national identity, where national identity can be understood as follows: "... a vision of everything that exists, where vision = sensory perception = logical comprehension + evaluation (on two levels), and everything that exists = objective material world + brought into it by human consciousness (subjective assessments / emotional and value/and mythical categories" (V.Kornilov, 2003). National-cultural identification is a multifaceted concept concerning such aspects of human life as psychology, sociologization, communication, culture, language. All this explains the presence of a large number of approaches to the study of this concept. One of the first scientists to address the problem of national identity was in the XIX century. V. Humboldt, applying the concept of internal form in relation to language (innere Sprachform), linking with its help the

external forms of language with mental processes. Humboldt managed to formulate for the first time the position on the relationship between the nature of the language and the character of the people: "... different languages in their essence, in their influence on different feelings, are in fact different worldviews", "the originality of the language affects the essence of the nation, therefore, a thorough study of the language should include everything, what history and philosophy associate with the inner world of man" (V.Humboldt, 1985).

Through language, a person learns the national culture, the national culture dictates the appearance of certain words in the language. These are two tools for understanding hidden linguistic and cultural information. It becomes obvious that the concept of the cultural code and its reflection in the language cannot but be ambiguous. Fairy tales and one of the modern forms of their implementation – animated films – can be considered one of the striking examples of encoding national-linguistic identity, potentially aimed at forming the mentality of the younger generation by means of multimedia texts. It should be noted that as society develops, the conceptual picture of fairy tales for children and adults undergoes significant changes. This applies to the behavior and statements of characters, in particular, animated films belonging to different social strata, age groups, national cultures.

Modern animated films, which include the Russian animated series "Smeshariki", which became the object of this study, naturally reflect the linguistic picture of the world of the country creating the animated film. Considering the phenomenon of animation in the framework of this work, it can be noted that in the analyzed type of films, the function of socialization, aimed at educational, cognitive, developmental impact, and aesthetic are more pronounced, a function that manifests itself in a multifaceted and multidirectional impact on the target audience. The socializing effect of animation is to simplify the process of integrating the child as the main recipient of animated products into the system of social relations.

The creation of an animated film, involving the realization of the author's(s) intention, aimed at the realization of such tasks as writing a script, which is a discursive whole with a purposeful selection of words, phrases and other semiotic phrases, reflects the current processes taking place in modern society at the time of creation. Discursivity as a direct component of an animated video verbal product, it also consists in transmitting to the audience linguistic and cultural national features, as well as cultural realities encoded in the lexical structure of the transmitted text as a unit of discourse and influencing the

passage of the process of adaptive translation of this type of film text in the localization process.

There are a significant number of animated films, primarily produced by studios in the USA, where national identity is not so important, since films were immediately created with the prospect of translation and localization. Rather, national identity was imitated, stereotyped images were used, which could be identified as belonging to some ethnic group: "Madagascar" ("Madagascar", DreamWorks Animation, 2005) – stereotyped Malagasy, «Teenage Mutant Ninja Turtles» ("TMNT», IMAGE, 2007) – as if Japanese, "Mulan" ("Mulan» Walt Disney Pictures, 1998), "Kung Fu Panda" ("Kung Fu Panda", DreamWorks Animation, 2008) – Chinese, etc.

Such films can be considered as a socio-cultural phenomenon, forming and reflecting both the conventional picture of the world of a certain ethnic group, and the linguistic and cultural picture of the world of an individual and society as a whole. Animated films, like motion pictures, present images of the culture in which they were created. The tradition of creating animated films (animated television series) is not new. In the Western film and television industry, such series appeared, as a rule, after the release of a full-length animated film that had commercial success, actually exploiting and developing its plot. Almost all successful full-length animated films were turned into TV series and went through the localization process.

A striking example is the animated film of 1989 "The Little Mermaid" by Disney studio, which later turned into a series translated into many languages of the world. It is worth noting one of the features of English-language children's animation: its language, both semiotic and verbal, is as universal as possible (if we consider English as, in fact, the language of interethnic communication). The pragmatics of foreign animated series is obvious – commercial success is at the forefront, requiring maximum coincidence of stereotypical images, the use of short dialogues, simplifying the translation and localization process.

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